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Teaching Professional French-Language Vocabulary to Future Journalists in the University Education System

Oksana Romanenko

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor, Associate Professor of the Department of International Relations of the Institute of Economics and Business Education, State University of Economics and Technology, Kryvyi Rih, Ukraine,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5129-9135>

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***Abstract: Objective.** The substantiation of the methodological foundations for teaching professional French-language vocabulary to future journalists within the Ukrainian university education system, in response to contemporary demands for renewed foreign language training of media communication specialists.*

***Methods.** The study employed analysis of scholarly literature, synthesis of theoretical approaches, comparative analysis of methodological systems, and generalization of pedagogical experience in teaching French as a second foreign language in higher education institutions. The linguopragmatic, communicative, and competence-based approaches were examined as conceptual frameworks for professional vocabulary acquisition among journalism students.*

***Results.** The lexical features of French-language mass media were characterized, and the specifics of their application in journalistic practice were identified. The competence-based approach was established as the determining factor in foreign language instruction for future journalists, as it ensures the development of*

not only linguistic but also intercultural and media-communicative competencies. A system of practical exercises was developed, aimed at activating professional vocabulary, working with authentic digital media texts, and completing communicative tasks that simulate real journalistic situations. The significance of integrating contextual learning with online resources for developing the ability to adapt vocabulary to various text genres, target audiences, and media platforms was substantiated.

Conclusions. *Teaching professional French-language vocabulary requires a systematic approach that integrates theoretical language study with its practical application in professional communicative situations. Developing skills in analytical thinking, critical source evaluation, and intercultural communication constitutes an essential component in preparing competitive media communication specialists. The research findings may be applied in designing educational and methodological materials for French language courses for journalism students.*

Keywords: *French as a second foreign language, media lexicon, intercultural competence, communicative approach, professional training of media specialists.*

Навчання професійної франкомовної лексики майбутніх журналістів в системі університетського навчання

Романенко Оксана Василівна

кандидат педагогічних наук, доцент, доцент кафедри міжнародних відносин
навчально-наукового інституту економіки та бізнес-освіти, Державний
університет економіки і технологій, вул. Медична, 16, м. Кривий Ріг, 50005,
Україна, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5129-9135>

Анотація: *Мета статті* – обґрунтування методологічних засад навчання професійної франкомовної лексики майбутніх журналістів у системі університетської освіти України в умовах оновлення іншомовної підготовки фахівців з медіакомунікацій.

Методи. У дослідженні застосовано аналіз наукової літератури, синтез теоретичних підходів, порівняльний аналіз методичних систем та узагальнення педагогічного досвіду викладання французької мови як другої іноземної у закладах вищої освіти. Лінгвопрагматичний, комунікативний і компетентнісний підходи розглядалися як концептуальні основи формування фахового вокабуляру студентів журналістських спеціальностей.

Результати. Схарактеризовано лексичні особливості франкомовних засобів масової інформації та визначено специфіку їх застосування в журналістській практиці. Встановлено, що компетентнісний підхід є визначальним у навчанні іноземної мови майбутніх журналістів, оскільки забезпечує формування не лише лінгвістичної, а й міжкультурної та медіакомунікативної компетентностей. Розроблено систему практичних вправ, спрямованих на активізацію фахового словникового запасу, роботу з автентичними текстами цифрових медіа та виконання комунікативних завдань, що моделюють реальні журналістські ситуації. Обґрунтовано важливість інтеграції контекстного навчання з онлайн-ресурсами для формування здатності адаптувати лексику до різних текстових жанрів, цільових аудиторій і медіаплатформ.

Висновки. Навчання фахової франкомовної лексики потребує системного підходу, що поєднує теоретичне опрацювання мовного матеріалу з практикою його застосування у фахових комунікативних ситуаціях. Формування навичок аналітичного мислення, критичного оцінювання джерел і міжкультурної комунікації є невід'ємним складником підготовки конкурентоспроможного фахівця у сфері медіакомунікацій. Результати дослідження можуть бути

використані при розробленні навчально-методичного забезпечення курсів французької мови для студентів журналістських спеціальностей.

Ключові слова: французька мова як друга іноземна, медіалексика, міжкультурна компетентність, комунікативний підхід, фахова підготовка медіафахівців.

Introduction. Modern journalism operates in a globalized information society, where the speed of data processing, accuracy, and stylistic adequacy of language determine professional efficiency and ensure a consistently high level of competence among mass media specialists. Knowledge of foreign languages, in particular French, constitutes an integral component of a future journalist's professional profile, given that French occupies a prominent position in international media, organizations, and platforms. Command of professional French-language vocabulary enables work with authentic sources, participation in international projects, content creation for Francophone audiences, and the development of intercultural competence.

The National Doctrine for the Development of Education of Ukraine in the 21st Century emphasizes the provision of high-quality higher education and the labor market mobility of university graduates [21, p. 11]. This policy orientation underscores the considerable importance of French language proficiency in the training of future mass communications specialists within the university education system. In recent years, increasing emphasis has been placed on French as a second or third foreign language alongside English, a shift that in no way diminishes its relevance or significance. Moreover, French-language journalistic texts extend well beyond professional terminology, serving as an extensive source of stylistic devices, figurative constructions, set expressions, and clichés; as such, they function as effective instructional material for immersive acquisition of this European language with its rich historical and contemporary heritage.

Literature review. Issues of professional training of future journalists, in particular the formation of speech and foreign language competence, the development of professional communicative skills, and the use of modern pedagogical technologies and digital resources in the educational process, have been the subject of research by many Ukrainian scholars. The practical aspects of forming the professional foreign language competence of future journalists in the process of their professional training are examined in the study by I. Chemeris [29]. The research focuses on the use of professionally oriented learning tasks that contribute to the development of students' speech skills and the formation of their ability to effectively apply a foreign language in the field of media communication. Particular attention is paid to the importance of combining language training with models of real professional journalistic situations.

The theoretical and practical foundations of forming the speech competence of future journalists within professional training are investigated by N. Ponomarenko et al. [24]. The study substantiates the importance of systematic work with texts of various genres, as well as the development of skills for information analysis and the creation of professionally oriented speech. Considerable attention is also given to the integration of language training with practical types of journalistic activity, which contributes to the formation of communicative readiness of future media professionals.

Professional requirements for the journalistic profession from the perspective of the competence-based approach to training future specialists are analyzed in the study by M. Butyrina et al. [11]. The research identifies the main groups of competencies required for a modern journalist, among which communicative, information-analytical, and speech competencies occupy a particularly important place. It is emphasized that the formation of a high level of language culture is an essential component of professional training for specialists in the field of mass communications.

The significance of guest lectures in the process of forming the practical competencies of future journalists is explored by O. Markiv et al. [19]. The study demonstrates that the involvement of media practitioners in the educational process

contributes to the deepening of students' professional knowledge, the development of their communicative skills, and a better understanding of the real conditions of the media industry. Such a format of educational interaction allows theoretical training to be effectively combined with practical professional experience.

Modern methods of teaching foreign languages in a distance learning format under the conditions of martial law and the transformation of the educational environment are analyzed by O. Rachkovskyi et al. [25]. The research emphasizes the use of digital platforms, interactive technologies, and multimedia resources as effective tools for supporting students' language training. The approaches discussed contribute to the development of students' foreign language communicative competence and ensure the adaptation of the educational process to new social and technological conditions.

European integration processes as an important factor in improving the professional competencies of journalists are examined in the study by A. Blyzniuk et al. [9]. The authors highlight the significance of developing linguistic, intercultural, and communicative competencies as key components of modern training for media professionals. Considerable attention is also paid to the need to harmonize journalism educational programs with European standards of professional training.

The development of speech skills of future media professionals on the basis of a comprehensive pedagogical approach is studied by A. Lisnevskaya et al. [18]. The research substantiates the expediency of combining theoretical language training with practical types of communicative activities aimed at forming students' professional speech. According to the researchers, the application of a comprehensive approach ensures the preparation of future journalists for effective work with information in the modern media environment.

The development of digital literacy of future journalists as an important direction of modern scientific and pedagogical research is analyzed by I. Huzii et al. [13]. The study pays particular attention to the role of digital technologies in shaping the

professional competencies of media specialists and preparing them for work in the digital information environment. The research emphasizes the necessity of integrating digital tools into the process of professional training for journalists.

The role of media production in the professional training of future journalists is investigated by V. Bashmanivskiy et al. [8]. The study reveals the importance of practical skills in creating media content and developing the ability to work with different formats of informational materials. Particular attention is devoted to combining theoretical knowledge with practical activities in the field of modern media.

The application of interactive learning technologies in the training of future journalists is examined in the research by I. Demeshko [15]. The study substantiates the effectiveness of using discussions, role-playing games, and other interactive methods for developing students' professional communicative skills. The implementation of such pedagogical technologies contributes to the activation of students' learning activities and the formation of professionally oriented speech skills among future media specialists.

Discourse in its various manifestations has been examined by both Ukrainian and foreign researchers: K. Kusko addressed the discourse of personal communication [17], T. Veckur described its theoretical aspects [12], and T. van Dijk and M. Stubbs analyzed the linguistic dimensions of discourse [5; 6]. V. Borisov explores the relationship between discourse and text [10], A. Davidenko examines the theoretical and methodological aspects of translation [14], and I. Shevchenko argues for the study of discourse as a communicative and cognitive phenomenon [30].

Professional French vocabulary constitutes one of the most dynamically evolving layers of the contemporary French lexical system. The rapid development of information technologies, global media, and cross-cultural communication has generated a substantial influx of new lexical units into French journalistic discourse, ranging from terminological borrowings to professionalisms with restricted domains of use. As V. Kosiak demonstrates, the integration of professional vocabulary and

restricted-use terminology into the French lexical system is a continuous process shaped by extralinguistic factors, including socio-political transformations and technological progress, as well as by internal word-formation mechanisms such as affixation, telescoping, and semantic derivation [16]. This finding carries particular significance for the methodology of teaching professional French vocabulary to future journalists, given that the lexical corpus they must master is not static but subject to ongoing renewal and stylistic redistribution across functional registers. The analysis of professionalisms, their structural characteristics, and their functional boundaries within scientific, journalistic, and colloquial styles provides an indispensable theoretical foundation for designing a professionally oriented curriculum in French as a second or third foreign language at Ukrainian universities.

Professional journalistic vocabulary is examined predominantly within the context of translation studies. The translation process has attracted considerable attention from both theorists and practitioners, and the problem of translation transformations remains a subject of sustained interest among domestic and foreign scholars. In the study of media texts, the linguopragmatic approach is applied to analyze the impact of textual meaning on public perception [20]. Nevertheless, the number of works devoted to the acquisition of professional French-language vocabulary by future public communications specialists studying French as a second foreign language in non-philological higher education institutions remains insufficient.

Scholarly perspectives diverge on the question of what constitutes the foundation of professional language instruction. Ukrainian researchers tend to define communicative competence primarily as the ability to work with text and information, whereas European scholars conceptualize media not only as a channel of information exchange but also as a form of social interaction, to be examined through the lens of an activity-based approach. In foreign language pedagogy, the principle that knowledge must be grounded in practical application is well established. No lexical unit or grammatical rule can be effectively acquired without systematic practice

through a series of targeted exercises. Accordingly, the concept of consolidating professional vocabulary through its active use in context has become a foundational principle in the methodology of professional language instruction. According to the decisions of the European Council, communicative competence constitutes the primary objective in foreign language instruction, as it enables students to discuss problems, articulate and defend positions, develop critical and creative thinking, and adapt to the language environment [22, p. 197].

The professional vocabulary of journalists is examined and analyzed predominantly within the context of translation activities, as evidenced by the extensive body of work of a philological nature. The linguopragmatic approach serves as the basis of language teaching and plays a central role in facilitating textual comprehension. This approach is particularly decisive in organizing the training of future translators, given its capacity to illuminate the pragmatic dimensions of meaning. I. Polyuk, for instance, examines the features of translating texts across different functional styles [23]. An analytical examination of the relationship between discourse, text, and hypertext in the context of digital communication is presented by U. Ahmadova, who defines discourse as a broad communicative structure with social, cultural, and cognitive dimensions, and text as the materialized linear realization of discourse available for interpretation [1]. The same researcher emphasizes that hypertext, as a non-linear form of textuality conditioned by digital technologies, transforms the production and perception of meaning by shifting the role of the addressee from passive recipient to active participant in the communicative process [1]. O. Semida identifies the principal characteristics of ineffective discourse [26]. Materials from French-language media sources are thus studied primarily through the lens of translation, with attention to philological precision; however, the conditions for teaching journalistic vocabulary to future international communications specialists within the university system, where French is acquired as a second or third foreign language, remain unexamined. For students required to attain functional command of

French within two to three years, the activity-based and communicative approaches are more appropriate than the linguopragmatic method, which is better suited to the training of future philologists. In this context, the competence-based approach proves most applicable, as it is oriented toward the formation of specific competencies, the principal of which is foreign language competence, constituting the primary objective of French instruction as a second foreign language.

The competence-based approach, initiated in Western European pedagogy and developed considerably over the past two decades, has demonstrated its effectiveness when implemented in accordance with European standards for foreign language instruction [2]. The formation of foreign language competence is achieved through the development of four interrelated language competencies, each assigned specific learning objectives that facilitate their attainment and structure the overall process of foreign language acquisition. A substantial number of Ukrainian researchers regard the competence-based approach as the most effective framework for developing successful communicative ability, as it provides the most precise parameters for defining the scope and objectives of foreign language study.

According to the requirements of the European Council, communicative competence constitutes the primary objective in foreign language instruction, as it equips students with the ability to discuss problems, articulate and defend positions, develop critical and creative thinking, and adapt to the language environment [27]. When a future specialist is expected to demonstrate a comprehensive set of professional competencies, the competence-based approach to foreign language learning proves to be the most appropriate and pedagogically sound framework for achieving this goal.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Despite the growing scholarly interest in professionally oriented foreign language teaching within Ukrainian higher education, a number of critical gaps remain inadequately addressed in the existing literature. The analysis of available studies reveals that research on teaching professional French-language vocabulary to future

journalists in non-philological higher education institutions is fragmentary and methodologically inconsistent, which significantly limits the capacity to design evidence-based instructional frameworks for this specific learner population.

First, the overwhelming majority of studies devoted to French journalistic discourse and professional lexis approach the subject from a philological or translation studies perspective. Researchers such as I. Polyuk [23], V. Borisov [10], and O. Semida [26] examine French media texts primarily as objects of translation or linguistic analysis rather than as pedagogical material for communicative language development. This creates a substantial disciplinary gap: the conditions under which future communications specialists acquire professional French vocabulary as a second or third foreign language in a non-philological educational environment remain largely unstudied.

Second, no systematic methodological framework has been developed for the formation of French-language professional lexical competence in journalism students who study the language within an accelerated university curriculum of two to three academic years. The specificity of this learner context, namely a compressed timeframe, a non-philological institutional setting, and the parallel demands of professional journalism training, requires a targeted pedagogical approach that existing studies do not provide. The competence-based and communicative approaches, while widely recognized in Ukrainian [22] and European pedagogical discourse [2], have not been operationalized in the form of a practical instructional system tailored to the formation of French media vocabulary in future journalists.

Third, the integration of digital media resources, authentic French-language online platforms, and multimedia journalism materials as active pedagogical instruments in vocabulary instruction has not been examined with sufficient empirical depth. Although H. Widdowson [7] and J.-P. Cuq [4] emphasize the centrality of authentic professional discourse in language acquisition, Ukrainian didactic practice at non-philological institutions largely continues to rely on static print-based materials,

leaving students insufficiently prepared for the dynamic, genre-diverse nature of contemporary French journalism. The development of digital communication has further transformed journalistic discourse, introducing new textual forms and modes of interaction that, as U. Ahmadova demonstrates, require learners to navigate non-linear hypertext structures alongside traditional media formats [1].

Fourth, the intercultural dimension of professional vocabulary instruction, specifically the competence to interpret culturally embedded meaning in French media texts, has not been adequately theorized or practically addressed in the context of Ukrainian journalism education. Professional French vocabulary carries significant sociocultural, historical, and political connotations that cannot be acquired through decontextualized lexical memorization [4]; yet no structured approach to developing this intercultural layer of lexical competence has been proposed for the target learner group. The capacity for critical analysis of media content, recognized as an indispensable professional skill [28; 3], remains insufficiently integrated into French vocabulary instruction at Ukrainian non-philological institutions. As V. Kosiak establishes, the lexical corpus of professional French is not static but subject to continuous renewal driven by both extralinguistic factors and internal word-formation mechanisms [16], which further underscores the necessity of dynamic, practice-oriented approaches that current scholarship has yet to develop for the specific context of journalism education in Ukraine.

Formulation of the article's objectives. Given that the question of teaching professional French-language journalistic vocabulary to future mass communications specialists in non-philological higher education institutions has not been systematically addressed in the existing literature, the objective of the present study is the identification of effective methods for teaching professional French-language vocabulary and the development of practical recommendations for integrating this vocabulary into the educational process in order to foster students' professional readiness. The main objectives of the study are as follows: to analyze the concept of

professional vocabulary, to characterize French-language journalistic lexis, to examine contemporary approaches to language instruction within the university education system, and to develop proposals for the practical application of acquired vocabulary aimed at forming students' readiness for future professional activity.

The hypothesis of the present study holds that successful mastery of professional vocabulary by future journalists and mass communications specialists is attainable only through the active use of acquired lexical units in practice, specifically in professional communicative situations that must be systematically created within foreign language instruction. The effective teaching of professional vocabulary to journalism students in the university education system, under the condition that future international communications specialists study French as a second foreign language, is contingent upon the application of a competence-based approach, which is oriented toward the formation of specific student competencies, the principal of which is foreign language competence.

Research results. The primary task of a mass media specialist is to obtain, analyze, and present substantial volumes of information with absolute accuracy and precision, while accounting for the needs of the target audience. This requires thorough command of foreign language vocabulary, awareness of native language norms, and mastery of the stylistic resources of foreign-language journalistic discourse, alongside proficiency in contemporary text-processing tools. Professional vocabulary constitutes the foundation of journalistic training, as it ensures the accuracy and accessibility of information while forming the stylistic adequacy of the text. It encompasses terms, set phrases, and clichés that reflect the specific nature of journalistic activity. Solid command of such vocabulary enables students to produce news reports, analytical materials, interviews, and feature texts, thereby constructing a coherent communicative framework for professional activity.

A distinctive feature of French professional journalistic vocabulary is the relatively high proportion of lexical units whose meaning is readily interpretable by

Ukrainian speakers. Lexical items such as *les médias*, *la rédaction*, *le rédacteur/la rédactrice*, *le/la journaliste*, *la dépêche*, *le reportage*, and *le reporter* are generally accessible to beginner-level learners and are therefore recommended as initial instructional material. When addressing the topic of profession or *métier*, instruction should begin with an analysis of journalism-related occupations. Terms such as *un pigiste*, denoting a freelance journalist compensated per unit of work, *un envoyé spécial*, referring to a special correspondent, and *un rédacteur en chef*, meaning editor-in-chief, merit particular attention. The study of such vocabulary should also address the grammatical properties of profession-denoting nouns, including masculine and feminine forms and the use of articles. Students should be introduced to the term *la Une*, a feminine article construction designating the front page of a newspaper. The meaning of the title of the satirical magazine *Canard enchaîné* may be explained by the instructor or assigned as an independent interpretive task.

Despite the apparent accessibility of basic journalistic vocabulary, the comprehension of French-language journalistic texts presents considerable difficulty, as the majority of such texts are markedly political in character and grounded in the regional, historical, philosophical, and sociocultural context of France. Readers unfamiliar with French history, world politics, or cultural heritage will encounter significant challenges in constructing meaning from such material.

French journalistic vocabulary is characterized by dynamism and high adaptability, undergoing continuous renewal through borrowings, neologisms, and abbreviations. Numerous terms have entered the French language from English, reflecting the rapid development of digital journalism as a defining feature of a digitalized society. Anglicisms such as *blog*, *breaking news*, *cross-media journalism*, *fact-checking*, *flash journalism*, and *podcast* are relatively accessible to Ukrainian learners, as many of these terms have been adopted into Ukrainian as well. Certain contemporary terms associated with digital journalism emerge more rapidly than they can be incorporated into instructional materials, making engagement with authentic

media an essential tool for vocabulary acquisition. Contemporary media practice evolves continuously, and its developments are reflected immediately in journalistic output. Print publications do not always keep pace with digital journalism, which reproduces current reality with immediacy. Present-day audiences, particularly younger generations, obtain information predominantly from online sources rather than print. Future journalists must therefore develop a clear understanding of which professional terms and lexical units to select in order to convey the substance of news accurately to their readership. As L. Shcherba observes, the lexical composition of a language constitutes its most dynamic element [31, p. 120], and the vocabulary of news and analytical genres differs accordingly in both stylistic register and functional orientation.

Podcast-based tasks are an effective instrument for developing students' communicative competence. Instruction should proceed from accessible topics toward progressively more complex material, so that comprehension speed and thematic range expand with each task. Such activities develop listening skills with authentic materials, enrich vocabulary, and foster both dialogic and monologic speech production. Podcast assignments should be differentiated according to proficiency level and should offer learners a choice of topics. Consistent engagement with such tasks, combined with gradual increases in complexity, supports measurable progress in language acquisition.

Understanding these nuances is essential for students' professional development. Instructors should not only clarify the meaning of terms but also illuminate their stylistic and pragmatic functions within authentic media texts, thereby enabling students to develop language competence approaching a professional standard.

Contemporary methods of teaching professional vocabulary integrate communicative, lexical, and contextual approaches. H. Widdowson argues that language learning becomes effective only when learners engage with authentic discourse [7, p. 18], underscoring the centrality of authentic material in the instruction of mass media communication specialists.

Cuq J.-P., whose extensive research on Francophonie led to the conceptual elaboration of French as a second foreign language, maintains that teaching specialized vocabulary should be grounded in concrete professional situations [4, p. 69]. This principle implies that instruction must extend beyond lexical memorization to encompass the active use of vocabulary in professional communicative contexts, with explicit attention to style, genre, and audience.

Accordingly, students should analyze texts across a range of genres, including news reports, analytical commentary, feature articles, and interviews, identifying set phrases and terms before applying them in their own writing. In working with reports, for instance, students may employ the expression *à la une* for headlines or *en direct* to signal live coverage, thereby producing professionally appropriate texts.

The contextual approach situates vocabulary acquisition within authentic communicative environments. Engagement with sources such as *Le Monde*, *Libération*, *France 24*, and *Paris Hebdo* enables students to observe how lexical units function across different genres, examine tone and stylistic register, and evaluate the pragmatic role of vocabulary in context.

Effective instruction in professional French vocabulary requires a comprehensive methodology that integrates traditional and contemporary approaches. Instructors draw on vocabulary exercises, authentic text analysis, role-play simulations of professional scenarios, interactive online platforms, and multimedia materials. This framework enables students not only to retain terminology but to apply it in real communicative situations, reinforcing the principle that vocabulary must be encountered repeatedly across varied textual contexts, analyzed for meaning, and activated through practical tasks.

The following task types are recommended for integration into the instructional process. Students may be assigned to work with news websites such as *Le Monde* and *France 24*, identifying keywords and clichés and analyzing their use in headlines and body text. The production of original news reports using newly acquired vocabulary

provides structured practice in active lexical application. Engagement with podcasts and radio broadcast materials, followed by discussion of the issues raised and analysis of the linguistic tools employed, develops both receptive and productive competence. Role-play activities in which students assume the role of a journalist at a press conference or live broadcast simulate authentic professional communication and reinforce vocabulary use. A role-play task modeled on a job interview format may be used to examine the advantages and professional demands of journalism as a career. Discussion of editorial assignments, including the formulation of objectives and the elaboration of implementation strategies, develops both communicative and professional reasoning skills.

Contextual learning enables students to understand the function of a lexical unit not only as a dictionary entry but also within real journalistic discourse. The expression *en direct*, for instance, denotes live coverage in a television news context, yet may carry a metaphorical meaning in a feature article, emphasizing the immediacy of the event described.

An equally effective approach in the training of future journalists is genre-based text work. News articles demand accuracy and objectivity, analytical texts require a broad argumentative vocabulary, and interviews rely on conventional discourse markers and set phrases to sustain dialogue. Students may be assigned comparative genre tasks in which they identify genre-specific vocabulary and apply it in their own writing.

Practical tasks designed to facilitate professional vocabulary acquisition may include the construction of semantic fields around journalistic terms, identification of word families, composition of examples, and analysis of usage patterns. Word-focused activities such as definition matching, gap-fill exercises, error correction, headline selection, and single-word summarization tasks reinforce lexical retention. Analysis of authentic texts with attention to the distinction between informational content and rhetorically motivated passages develops critical reading competence.

The cultivation of critical thinking skills constitutes an essential component of journalism education [28; 3], as the capacity to analyze information and evaluate its truthfulness is a defining requirement of the profession.

Digital resources considerably expand instructional opportunities. Language learning platforms, online dictionaries, video materials, and podcasts enable students to engage with authentic professional discourse, develop receptive competence in the target language, and apply vocabulary through interactive tasks.

Podcast-based instruction serves multiple pedagogical functions: it allows students to observe professional vocabulary in use, develops their capacity to articulate positions on current issues in French, cultivates accurate and contextually appropriate deployment of professional terminology, and promotes awareness of intonation and stylistic features. Lexical units acquired through this medium may subsequently be activated in students' own production, including short reports and interviews.

The authentic resources of TV5 Monde offer a valuable instrument for the development of independent foreign language competence outside the classroom, supporting both individual learning trajectories and professional skill formation in extracurricular contexts.

H. Widdowson asserts that authentic multimedia input enhances comprehension and contextual learning [7, p. 25], thereby underscoring the pedagogical importance of authentic media engagement for the development of professional competence.

The acquisition of professional French vocabulary extends beyond purely linguistic training and necessarily encompasses the development of intercultural competence, which enables the journalist to interpret the cultural dimensions of both text and audience with accuracy.

Specialists in international media communication must develop a thorough understanding of the social context embedded in periodical press materials. Engagement with French digital and print publications is most productive when accompanied by knowledge of France's democratic traditions and the historical depth

of its civic and protest movements. The extensive network of public organizations and associations that characterizes French civil society constitutes valuable instructional material, as its study contributes not only to language acquisition but also to the formation of broader sociocultural awareness.

Cuq J.-P. maintains that understanding specialized language necessarily involves understanding the associated cultural practices [4, p. 75], which confirms that the development of intercultural competence constitutes an indispensable component of future journalists' professional training, as it enables the avoidance of misinterpretation and the formation of an adequate professional discourse.

An equally important dimension of contemporary language training for journalists is the integration of theory and practice. The acquisition of professional French vocabulary requires systematic engagement with authentic texts, targeted vocabulary exercises, and the integration of lexical units into various genres of journalistic writing.

Practical tasks include peer and self-editing activities involving detailed error analysis and correction. The review of written materials should encompass the assessment of stylistic appropriateness, terminological accuracy, and genre relevance, all of which foster critical thinking and linguistic flexibility. The production of any text intended for public dissemination constitutes a concrete application of acquired knowledge, while the organization of role-play activities reinforces the use of professional vocabulary in simulated contexts. This approach enables students not only to expand their lexical range but also to internalize the function of each unit, including its stylistic and pragmatic role within a specific communicative situation.

Vocabulary acquired through oral tasks is consolidated through written exercises that integrate reading, listening, writing, and speaking in a coherent instructional sequence. Digest and review tasks require students to select keywords, formulate headlines, and compose concise summaries using authentic terminology. Stylistic transformation exercises, such as converting news reports into analytical texts or

reversing the process, develop sensitivity to genre-specific vocabulary use. Digital content analysis tasks involving podcasts, videos, and online news articles situate vocabulary acquisition in a dynamic context and build capacity for rapid comprehension. Collectively, such exercises develop an active vocabulary and cultivate skills in lexical analysis and genre adaptation.

The training of future journalists through foreign language instruction encompasses not only linguistic development but also the formation of intercultural competence. Students are trained to account for the cultural profile of the target audience, the distinctive features of the Francophone media environment, and the sociocultural context of texts drawn from mass media sources.

Conclusions. The findings of the present study support the following conclusions. The teaching of professional French-language vocabulary to future journalists in non-philological higher education institutions constitutes a complex, multi-component process comprising several sequential stages. The initial stage involves familiarization with professional lexical units through the study of journalistic texts and media materials, with the aim of forming students' foreign language competence.

The second stage entails the application of acquired terminology in practical tasks and genre-differentiated texts. The linguopragmatic approach to professional journalistic vocabulary acquisition enables students to deploy studied lexical units and collocations appropriately, in accordance with the communicative purpose, intent, and specific task requirements.

At the stage devoted to processing vocabulary associated with the future profession of a mass communications specialist, students are assigned tasks oriented not only toward the automatization of professional terms, phrases, and verbal constructions, but also toward preparation for future professional activity.

The integration of digital media into instruction enables students to develop a current, flexible, and dynamic French vocabulary. Engagement with authentic sources

provides a comprehensive representation of contemporary political and social life in France, thereby contributing to the formation of students' sociocultural competence.

The effectiveness of vocabulary instruction depends on the coherent combination of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, sustained repetition, and the active use of lexical units across varied communicative situations. The following recommendations are proposed: to incorporate interactive tasks that simulate professional contexts, fostering natural and competent performance under varied conditions; to prioritize authentic media materials as the basis for exposure to contemporary French; to activate lexical units systematically in both written and oral tasks, given that written practice facilitates consolidation; and to develop all four language competencies through the use of professional vocabulary, with consistent attention to its sociocultural dimensions.

The training of future journalists within French as a second foreign language instruction thus assumes a comprehensive character, integrating knowledge, practice, and media text analysis, and enabling the formation of professionally competent specialists prepared to operate in the contemporary globalized information environment.

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